

Permafrost thaw challenges and life in Svalbard

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ABSTRACT

Svalbard is facing changes related to climate change and permafrost thaw, which have impacts on the life and well-being of people. This study evaluated impacts of climate change and permafrost thaw on the life of locals living in Longyearbyen, Svalbard and focused on investigating self-rated health, well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life, and feeling of empowerment when facing the changes and impacts. The aim was to find out which perceived environmental and adaptation factors relate to these dependent variables. The data was collected using a multidisciplinary questionnaire ($n = 84$); for statistical analysis cross-tabulation was used and the associations were tested either by the Pearson χ^2 test or Fisher's exact test, when appropriate. Binary logistic regression analysis was used to investigate associations between the dependent variables and perceived environmental and adaptation factors. Results suggested that well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life, and life balance (a sum variable of earlier parameters) were associated with the recognized challenges related to infrastructure or physical environment. Quality of life and life balance were supported by the opinion that not enough has been done to adapt to permafrost thaw by national and global authorities. Despite recognized challenges, participants appear to live satisfied lives. People seemed to have knowledge about the impacts of permafrost thaw, they wanted to adapt to the changes, but more actions are needed from national and global authorities. Research with a larger sample size is needed due to the complexity of the relationships between people, holistic well-being, and climate change.

1. Introduction

The Arctic is warming rapidly, resulting for example in a decrease of glaciers, ice and snow cover, and a rise in sea level and humidity, but also permafrost thaw and coastal erosion are central problems (IPCC, 2014; Stern et al., 2012). Based on the research evidence, Svalbard in particular is facing serious challenges. Climate change is occurring even faster (even four times higher) and changes are more visible than other Arctic areas (Ding et al., 2018; Flyen et al., 2020). Annual air temperature has been 1.0–1.2 °C higher / decade, and especially temperature rise during wintertime has been more visible, with a 2–3 °C increase (Førland et al., 2011; Onarheim et al., 2014). Warming air temperature, the reduction of sea ice is fast as well; winter ice loss in particular has been around 10% / decade (years 1979–2012), while summer ice loss has been around half from winter ice (Onarheim et al., 2014). As climate change continues, air temperature in winter is expected to increase and by the end of this century it may be approximately 10 °C higher than it currently is in Svalbard (Førland et al., 2011).

With its approximately 2300 inhabitants, the Norwegian town of Longyearbyen is the largest settlement on Svalbard, and its administrative center. The former coal mining town is today a highly modern, urban village with an increasingly international population. Tourism and the related service industry are growing rapidly, and together with research and higher education constitute the main economic pillars of what has become a post-industrial town. Longyearbyen's population is changing (Pedersen, 2017; Statistics Norway, 2020). Numbers from the local tax office show that today, around 30% of Longyearbyen's population is from outside Norway. The biggest minorities are from Thailand, Sweden, and the Philippines. The turnover in the population is extremely high, around 20%, meaning that approximately one in five inhabitants moves from Longyearbyen every year. In 2019, only 131 of Longyearbyen's inhabitants had lived there more than 20 years. There is a clear predominance of the 20–66 years age group (80.5%).

Jaskólski and colleagues have found that in Svalbard, visible impacts of climate change, such as altered landscape due to coastal erosion, landslides and permafrost thaw occur, resulting in negative impacts on

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infrastructure and the built environment (Jaskólski et al., 2018). Higher air temperatures will result in a deeper active layer, permafrost thaw, and further higher temperatures in the soil (Flyen et al., 2020). Infrastructure built on permafrost, e.g., wooden constructions, roads, buildings, and bridges are facing ongoing damages due to permafrost thaw (Flyen et al., 2020; Jaskólski et al., 2018). All these can have further impacts on residents' lives (Jaskólski et al., 2018).

Considering current research, climate change can affect peoples' health and well-being in several ways, directly or indirectly. Both ways may impact physically and mentally (Berry et al., 2010; Bourque and Cunsolo Willox, 2014; Hayes et al., 2018; McMichael, 2013; Palinkas and Wong, 2020). Extreme events and natural disasters in the environment, e.g., storms, floods, and extreme temperatures, can put human health and well-being at risk, causing injuries, even loss of lives (Bourque and Cunsolo Willox, 2014; McMichael, 2013; Cianconi et al., 2020; Ebi, 2011). Climate change might further increase the risk of infectious diseases transmitted through water, food, or animals (Ebi, 2011; Hambling et al., 2011; Solomon and LaRocque, 2019) and respiratory diseases (Ebi, 2011; Hambling et al., 2011). Additionally, events can challenge mental health and increase, for example, a feeling of mental burden, anxiety, and stress (Berry et al., 2010; Bourque and Cunsolo Willox, 2014; Cianconi et al., 2020; Solomon and LaRocque, 2019). Increased mental symptoms may result in serious mental disorders and illnesses, such as post-traumatic stress disorder and depression (Bourque and Cunsolo Willox, 2014; McMichael, 2013; Cianconi et al., 2020). Moreover, impacts can result in economic problems or damage to the physical or social environment (Berry et al., 2010; Bourque and Cunsolo Willox, 2014; Palinkas and Wong, 2020). Similarly, impacts of permafrost thaw, specifically on culture and the built environment, were observed among Indigenous people in Greenland and they affected the regular life of people (Timlin et al., 2021a; Timlin et al., 2021b). Still, recognizing that challenges are associated with infrastructure or culture very importantly seemed to increase the feeling of life satisfaction (Timlin et al., 2021a), and similarly, with the physical environment, it increased the feeling of life satisfaction and empowerment (Timlin et al., 2021a; Timlin et al., 2021b). Based on the literature, health and well-being have holistic aspects covering mental, physical, and social well-being (Rautio et al., 2014; WHO, 1946), and also spiritual well-being (Rautio et al., 2014). Health does not only refer to illnesses (WHO, 1946). According to Ryan and Deci (2001), an individual's mental well-being includes two parts: firstly, focusing on happiness and life satisfaction and secondly, being able to self-actualize and be socially active in life. Further, the feeling of empowerment supports pro-environmental behavior with a motivation for preventive actions for climate (Hartmann et al., 2018).

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impacts of climate change and permafrost thaw on the life of local people living in Longyearbyen, Svalbard. This study focused on investigating self-rated health, well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life, and feeling of empowerment when facing the changes and impacts of climate change and permafrost thaw. The specific aim was to find out which perceived environmental and adaptation factors relate to self-rated health, well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life, and feeling of empowerment.

2. Material and methods

Our study, as being part of the larger project, was led by social scientists and the used questionnaire was a result of a multidisciplinary effort. Researchers from different scientific disciplines (economy, engineering, anthropology, human geography, sociology and health sciences) used one questionnaire, with specific minor modifications for each case area of the project. The protocol of the multidisciplinary research did not meet the criteria of medical research involving human beings or ethical review in human sciences (Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK, 2019). This study did not collect any specific personal health information.

2.1. Data collection

A questionnaire was gathered in Longyearbyen ($n = 84$) between August 2019 and January 2020, by a researcher doing fieldwork. Over 70 participants answered using a printed paper version, the rest answered online. The participants were either interviewed directly by the researcher who filled out the questionnaires, allowing for a larger collection of qualitative data, or they filled out the survey themselves in absence of the researcher. Participants were informed about the project, how the data would be used, and that participation is anonymous and voluntary. The respondents were contacted by going from door to door, whereby the streets were chosen randomly, and through personal contacts and the snowball method. The face-to-face data gathering resulted in qualitative data in addition to the survey data, which complement the latter, adding context and depth. All subjects gave their oral consent for inclusion before they participated in the study.

2.2. Data analysis

The variables well-being, quality of life, and satisfaction with life were chosen in our questionnaire based on previous surveys, such as the project *Living conditions in the Arctic – SLiCA*, which used the same indicators to describe living conditions and well-being (Nordic Council of Ministers, Nordic Council of Ministers Secretariat, 2015; SliCA, 2015). In this current study, people were able to self-rate their well-being, quality of life, and satisfaction with life using the Likert scale (very bad, bad, OK, good, very good). Additionally, they were able to self-rate their health and whether they feel empowered to face changes related to permafrost thaw (feeling of empowerment). More research on feeling of empowerment in relation to climate change actions is needed (Hartmann et al., 2018). Fresque-Baxter and Armitage (2012) highlight the relationship between climate change and health and well-being, the understanding of the context in which people are living and facing the effects of climate change, and how they adapt to them and how people redefine their relationships to natural environment after changes.

Our questionnaire included altogether 44 questions, with specific questions concentrating on the impacts of permafrost thaw on the surrounding environment, adaptation, and questions related to the participant's current life situation. The questions that were chosen ($n = 21$) to describe and explain connections of permafrost thaw on self-rated health, well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life, and feeling of empowerment to face changes are presented in Appendix A.1.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Very good well-being, satisfaction with life and quality of life, compared to not very good (answers of OK or good) were used as dependent variables in the statistical analyses. This classification was used since only a few (4–15%) of 84 participants rated their well-being, quality of life or satisfaction with life as OK (Table 1). Additionally, a sum variable was summarized from variables of well-being, quality of life and satisfaction with life, with a range from 3 (OK) to 5 (very good). The sum variable was named “life balance” and it was classified into a lower group (named “not very strong” up to 12) and a higher group (named “very strong”, with a sum of 13–15). Therefore, the minimum level for very strong life balance was 87%. Cronbach's alpha of sum variable was 0.840. Furthermore, self-rated health was reclassified into three groups: low (0–33%), medium (34–66%) and high (67–100%). Originally, participants rated their health on a scale from 0 to 100. The feeling of empowerment to face changes related to permafrost thaw was reclassified as follows: no, somewhat / yes.

For the statistical analysis, specific reclassifications were made for independent variables. First, the variable of age was reclassified into three groups as follows: 18–34 years, 35–54 and over 55 years. Furthermore, the main professions were reclassified into groups for analysis: public sector (public administration, research / higher

Table 1
Demographic variables.

Demographic variables n (%)							Total
Age	18–24	25–34	35–44	45–54	55–64	≥ 65	
	15 (18)	29 (35)	20 (24)	12 (14)	6 (7)	2 (2)	84 (100)
Profession	Public sector	Private sector	Research, higher education	Extractive industry	Tourism	Student	Home-maker
	13 (16)	8 (10)	7 (8)	1 (1)	18 (21)	5 (6)	1 (1)
Nationality	Norwegian	Swedish	Filipino	Thai	Other		31 (37)
	52 (62)	8 (9)	3 (4)	1 (1)	20 (24)		84 (100)
Years lived in Svalbard	< 1 year	1–5 years	5–10 years	> 10 years			
	33 (38)	24 (29)	8 (10)	19 (23)			84 (100)
Consider Svalbard as “home”	No	Somewhat	Yes				
	11 (13)	14 (17)	42 (50)				84 (100)
Gender	Female	Male					
	39 (46)	45 (54)					84 (100)
Dependent variables, self-rated n (%)							
Health	Low	Medium	High				
	6 (7)	31 (37)	47 (56)				84 (100)
Well-being	OK	Good	Very good				
	5 (6)	33 (39)	46 (55)				84 (100)
Quality of life	OK	Good	Very good				
	4 (5)	33 (39)	47 (56)				84 (100)
Satisfaction with life	OK	Good	Very good				
	13 (15)	34 (41)	37 (44)				84 (100)
Empowered to face changes	No	Somewhat	Yes	Missing			
	19 (23)	34 (40)	30 (36)	1 (1)			84 (100)

education), private sector (private business, extractive industry), tourism (not reclassified), not employed (student, homemaker), and other (not reclassified). Participants who answered “other” ($n = 31$) informed having an occupation in the field of construction ($n = 14$), health / social / education system ($n = 7$), service industry ($n = 5$), they had several occupations ($n = 3$), or they were visiting Svalbard ($n = 2$). Also, the variable of nationality was reclassified into two different groups for statistical analysis: Norwegian / other alternative nationalities AND Scandinavian (Norwegian, Swedish and Danish) / other nationalities. The original choice of the questionnaire “other group” ($n = 20$) included one Danish participant and nationalities from other European countries ($n = 16$), South America ($n = 2$), and Asia ($n = 1$). Additionally, the variable of years lived on Svalbard (Q 42: How long have you been living in Svalbard) was regrouped in two ways, too: less than one year / 1–10 years / over 10 years AND less than 5 years / 5–10 years / over 10 years.

One participant gave two values (3, important and 4, very important) to question 5 (culture option). In the analysis, the medium value (4, very important) replaced both options. Relationships between independent variables were analyzed by cross-tabulation and the associations were tested either by the Pearson χ^2 test or Fisher's exact test, when appropriate. Variables having an association with any of these dependent variables (p -value ≤ 0.1) were chosen as predictors for a binary logistic regression model of each dependent variable (Appendix Tables B.2 and B.4). Binary logistic regression analysis (enter method) was used to investigate associations between perceived environmental / adaptation factors and very good well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life, very strong balanced life, and feeling of empowerment. Binary logistic regression analysis included two phases: univariate and multivariate analyses adjusted for demographic variables, e.g., age, gender, nationality (Scandinavian / others), and employment situation. For the regression analysis, the employment situation was reclassified into two groups: working / unemployed. This reclassification was completed based on the previous classification of the variable and the “other” group was relocated into the working group, excluding two participants who informed being visitors. Before conducting multivariate analysis, the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient values were checked to find possible correlations between independent variables.

Statistical data have been analyzed using IBM SPSS Software, version 25. Tests were two-tailed and a value of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Additionally, the original classification of

dependent variables was used and analyses were conducted for this classification as well: OK / good / very good. These results are presented in the Appendix tables (see Tables B.1. – B.4.) as they were like the results of the classification not very good (OK, good) / very good, which are reported in the results part of this paper. All the results having an association ≤ 0.1 are presented in appendix tables.

3. Results

3.1. General description of participants and associations of demographic variables

The largest group of the participants ($n = 29$, 35%) were aged between 25 and 34 years. Just over half of the participants were male ($n = 45$, 54%), and around a third of the participants ($n = 33$, 38%) have lived on Svalbard less than one year. (See Table 1.)

Age was significantly associated with satisfaction with life ($p = 0.036$). Younger participants aged 18–34 ($n = 26$, 55%) had lower satisfaction with life than two other groups. Men felt they were empowered to face changes related to permafrost thaw ($n = 21$, 70%) compared to women ($n = 9$, 30%, $p = 0.024$). (See Table 2.)

3.2. Associations of environmental factors

Being in the natural environment associated significantly with satisfaction with life and self-rated health. Those who were in the natural environment for recreational activities very often had very good satisfaction with life ($n = 27$, 73%), compared to those who were in nature less ($n = 10$, 27%, $p = 0.043$). Similarly, those who were in nature very often had high self-rated health ($n = 38$, 81%) compared to those who were in nature less ($n = 9$, 19%, $p < 0.001$). Challenges associated with living environment were significantly associated with dependent variables, except satisfaction with life. Those who assessed that challenges of thawing ground are associated with infrastructure (housing, buildings, roads) very importantly had very good well-being ($n = 40$, 87%, $p < 0.001$), quality of life ($n = 38$, 81%, $p = 0.004$), and very strong life balance ($n = 41$, 80%, $p = 0.005$) compared to those who assessed challenges as being less important or had lower well-being, quality of life and life balance. Opposite results were found with the feeling of empowerment as those who saw challenges of infrastructure as less important felt they were empowered to face changes ($n = 23$, 77%, $p =$

Table 2
Dependent variables and associations with demographic / perceived environmental factors ($p \leq 0.05$).

	Well-being				p-value
	Ok, good		Very good		
	n	(%)	n	(%)	
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads (n = 84)					
not important, a little important, important	16	(42)	2	(4)	<0.001
very important	19	(50)	40	(87)	
I don't know	3	(8)	4	(9)	
Challenges associated with the physical environment (n = 84)					
not important, a little important, important	22	(58)	15	(33)	0.012
very important	11	(29)	28	(61)	
I don't know	5	(13)	3	(6)	
	Quality of life				
	Ok, good		Very good		
	n	(%)	n	(%)	p-value
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads (n = 84)					
not important, a little important, important	14	(38)	4	(8)	0.004
very important	17	(36)	38	(81)	
I don't know	2	(5)	5	(11)	
	Satisfaction with life				
	Ok, good		Very good		
	n	(%)	n	(%)	p-value
Age (n = 84)					
18–34	26	(55)	18	(49)	0.036
35–54	20	(43)	12	(32)	
55 ≤	1	(2)	7	(19)	
Nationality (n = 84)					
Scandinavian	29	(62)	32	(87)	0.014
other	18	(38)	5	(13)	
Being in natural environmental for recreational activities (n = 84)					
never, rarely, sometimes	23	(49)	10	(27)	0.043
very often	23	(49)	27	(73)	
N/A	1	(2)	0	(0)	
	Life balance				
	not very strong		very strong		
	n	(%)	n	(%)	p-value
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads (n = 84)					
not important, a little important, important	13	(39)	5	(10)	0.005
very important	18	(55)	41	(80)	
I don't know	2	(6)	5	(10)	
	Feeling of empowerment				
	no, somewhat		yes		
	n	(%)	n	(%)	p-value
Gender (n = 83)					
female	30	(57)	9	(30)	0.024
male	23	(43)	21	(70)	
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads (n = 83)					
not important, a little important, important	26	(49)	23	(77)	0.044
very important	4	(8)	1	(3)	
I don't know	23	(43)	6	(20)	
Challenges associated with health (n = 83)					
not important, a little important	11	(21)	15	(50)	0.017
important, very important	26	(49)	11	(37)	
I don't know	16	(30)	4	(13)	
Lost picking spots due to flooded or submerged (n = 16)					
no	14	(26)	2	(7)	0.041
not answered	39	(74)	28	(93)	
	Health				
	low	medium	high		

Table 2 (continued)

	Well-being						p-value
	Ok, good		Very good		p-value		
	n	(%)	n	(%)			
Nationality (n = 84)	n	(%)	n	(%)	n	(%)	p-value
Norwegian	0	(0)	19	(61)	33	(70)	0.003
others	6	(100)	12	(39)	14	(30)	
Nationality (n = 84)							
Scandinavian	2	(33)	19	(61)	40	(85)	0.008
others	4	(67)	12	(39)	7	(15)	
Being in natural environment for recreational activities (n = 84)							
never, rarely, sometimes	6	(100)	18	(58)	9	(19)	<0.001
very often	0	(0)	12	(39)	38	(81)	
N/A	0	(0)	1	(3)	0	(0)	
Challenges associated with the physical environment (n = 84)							
not important, a little important, important	4	(67)	16	(51)	17	(36)	0.034
very important	0	(0)	12	(39)	27	(58)	
I don't know	2	(33)	3	(10)	3	(6)	

0.044) (See Table 2.)

3.3. Associations related to specific impacts and perceived adaptation factors

The majority of the participants with very good satisfaction with life assessed that permafrost thaw is causing problems to them personally ($n = 23, 62\%$) compared to those who did not recognize problems ($n = 14, 38\%, p = 0.015$). Moreover, most participants with high self-rated health assessed that thawing of the frozen ground is causing problems for them personally ($n = 26, 55\%$) and most of the participants with medium health assessed that it is not causing problems for them ($n = 18, 58\%, p = 0.032$). (See Table 3.)

The assessment that enough has not been done by national authorities to adapt or face impacts related to permafrost thaw was associated with well-being ($p = 0.040$), quality of life ($p = 0.027$) and life balance ($p = 0.003$). Most of the participants with very good well-being ($n = 22, 50\%$), quality of life ($n = 23, 51\%$) or very strong life balance ($n = 27, 55\%$) assessed that enough has not been done by national authorities compared to participants with lower well-being ($n = 14, 37\%$), quality of life ($n = 13, 35\%$) or life balance ($n = 9, 27\%$). (See Table 3.)

3.4. Associations between perceived environmental / adaptation factors and well-being, quality of life, satisfaction with life and feeling of empowerment

Feeling of empowerment to face changes was supported if the participant did not assess challenges associated with hunting and harvesting as important or very important (OR 5.60, $p = 0.034$, 95% CI 1.14–27.44). The situation was opposite with challenges associated with infrastructure (housing, buildings, roads) and the physical environment. The odds for very good well-being (OR 0.05, $p = 0.000$, 95% CI 0.01–0.26), quality of life (OR 0.13, $p = 0.003$, 95% CI 0.04–0.51) and very strong life balance (OR 0.14, $p = 0.004$, 95% CI 0.04–0.53) decreased if the participant assessed that challenges associated with housing, buildings and roads are less important, compared to those who assessed those challenges as being very important. A similar association was found with very good well-being (OR 0.26, $p = 0.010$, 95% CI 0.09–0.73) and satisfaction with life (OR 0.33, $p = 0.045$, 95% CI 0.11–0.98) and challenges related to the physical environment. (See Table 4.)

Very good satisfaction with life decreased (OR 0.31, $p = 0.033$, 95%

Table 3
Dependent variables and associations related to specific impacts and perceived adaptation factors ($p = \leq 0.05$).

	Well-being				p-value
	Ok, good		Very good		
	n	(%)	n	(%)	
Specific physical changes related to thawing of the frozen ground that most likely affect the community:					
deepening of the active layer (n = 30)	9	(24)	21	(46)	0.042
coastal erosion (n = 27)	7	(18)	20	(43)	0.019
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by individuals (n = 82)					
yes	12	(31)	2	(4)	0.002
somewhat	17	(45)	33	(75)	
no	9	(24)	9	(21)	
by national authorities (n = 82)					
yes	7	(18)	1	(2)	0.040
somewhat	17	(45)	21	(48)	
no	14	(37)	22	(50)	
Quality of life					
ok, good	n	(%)	very good	n	(%)
					p-value
Specific physical changes related to thawing of the frozen ground that most likely affect the community:					
deepening of the active layer (n = 30)	8	(22)	22	(47)	0.022
coastal erosion (n = 27)	7	(19)	20	(43)	0.033
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by individuals (n = 82)					
yes	12	(33)	2	(4)	0.001
somewhat	16	(43)	34	(76)	
no	9	(24)	9	(20)	
by national authorities (n = 82)					
yes	7	(19)	1	(2)	0.027
somewhat	17	(46)	21	(47)	
no	13	(35)	23	(51)	
Satisfaction with life					
ok, good	n	(%)	very good	n	(%)
					p-value
Thawing of the frozen ground causes problems, personally (n = 84)					
no	31	(66)	14	(38)	0.015
yes	16	(34)	23	(62)	
Specific physical changes related to thawing of the frozen ground that most likely affect the community:					
deepening of the active layer (n = 30)	9	(19)	21	(57)	0.001
coastal erosion (n = 27)	10	(21)	17	(46)	0.020
Life balance					
not very strong	n	(%)	very strong	n	(%)
					p-value
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by individuals (n = 82)					
yes	11	(33)	3	(6)	0.005
somewhat	16	(49)	34	(69)	
no	6	(18)	12	(25)	
by national authorities (n = 82)					
yes	7	(21)	1	(2)	0.003
somewhat	17	(52)	21	(43)	
no	9	(27)	27	(55)	
by the global community (n = 81)					
yes	6	(18)	1	(2)	0.016
somewhat	16	(49)	20	(42)	
no	11	(33)	27	(56)	
Feeling of empowerment					
yes					

Table 3 (continued)

	Well-being				p-value		
	Ok, good		Very good				
	n	(%)	n	(%)			
Thawing of the frozen ground is connected to other problems of individual / community (n = 83)							
no	3	(6)	4	(13)	0.020		
yes	30	(56)	23	(77)			
I don't know	20	(38)	3	(10)			
Specific physical changes related to thawing of the frozen ground that most likely affect the community:							
increase in rock fall (n = 42)	32	(60)	10	(33)	0.023		
Health							
low	n	(%)	medium	n	(%)		
			high	n	(%)		
					p-value		
Thawing of the frozen ground causes problems, personally (n = 84)							
no	6	(100)	18	(58)	21	(45)	0.032
yes	0	(0)	13	(42)	26	(55)	

CI 1.10–0.91) if the participant assessed that thawing of the frozen ground is not causing problems personally, compared to those who assessed that thawing causes problems. The odds for very good quality of life (OR 2.91, $p = 0.039$, 95% CI 1.06–8.01) and very strong life balance increased (OR 6.74, $p = 0.002$, 95% CI 2.05–22.14) if the participant felt that enough has not been done to adapt or face impacts by national authorities, compared to those who felt enough or somewhat enough has been done. A similar result was found with the assessment that not enough has been done by the global community, which supported very good quality of life (OR 3.02, $p = 0.034$, 95% CI 1.09–8.35) and very strong life balance (OR 4.88, $p = 0.006$, 95% CI 1.14–27.44). (See Table 4.)

The results of the univariate analysis are presented in Appendix Table B.5.

3.5. Open questions

Five themes emerged from the answers to the open questions (See Appendix A.1.). Themes were 1.) climate change is a natural cycle; 2.) not being familiar with climate change; 3.) changes noticed in nature; 4.) impacts on infrastructure, and; 5.) impacts on society and adaptation. Answers included some thoughts that climate change is not caused by humans and changes in nature are normal and natural. Additionally, people felt they do not necessarily have enough knowledge on climate change or impacts to provide further comments.

People felt that Svalbard's nature is changing, including thawing permafrost, increased temperatures, humidity and rain, less snow and changed sea ice, but also increased pollution levels. Mudslides, avalanches, and landslides were noticed. Changes were seen as risks and being in nature had become more dangerous. Further, the risk of polar bears coming near people was perceived as having increased. Similarly, changes in buildings, roads, and generally in infrastructure were observed. Some buildings and roads were observed to be destroyed, and the situation was perceived as getting worse every year. All these observations in nature and living environment caused feelings of worry and insecurity. Overall, nature appeared to be important for people and had a relaxation dimension.

Still, people felt there is a possibility to adapt to these changes, and that there is no other choice. The future needs to be saved and for some, the process had already started; for example, new buildings are built that are adapted to a changing climate. Adaptation was felt to be related to

Table 4
Multivariate analysis: Associations between dependent variables and perceived environmental and adaptation factors ($p \leq 0.05$).

Variables	Yes (n / %) / total	OR	95% CI	p-value
Challenges associated with the physical environment^a	Very good well-being			
not important, a little important, important very important	15 (40%) / 37	0.26	0.09–0.73	0.010
<i>Model statistics AIC 103,614; R² 0.172; HL: χ^2 9,113; df 8; p 0.333</i>	28 (72%) / 39	Ref.		
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads^a				
not important, a little important, important very important	2 (11%) / 18	0.05	0.01–0.26	<0.001
<i>Model statistics AIC 93,433; R² 0.341; HL: χ^2 7,048; df 7; p 0.341</i>	40 (68%) / 59	Ref.		
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads^a	Very good quality of life			
not important, a little important, very important	4 (22%) / 18	0.13	0.04–0.51	0.003
<i>Model statistics AIC 99,664; R² 0.257; HL: χ^2 5,390; df 7; p 0.613</i>	38 (64%) / 59	Ref.		
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by national authorities^a				
no	23 (64%) / 36	2.91	1.06–8.01	0.039
<i>Model statistics AIC 112,325; R² 0.162; HL: χ^2 7,429; df 7; p 0.386</i>	22 (48%) / 46	Ref.		
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by the global community^a				
no	24 (63%) / 38	3.02	1.09–8.35	0.034
<i>Model statistics AIC 110,665; R² 0.170; HL: χ^2 3,105; df 7; p 0.875</i>	20 (46%) / 43	Ref.		
Being in nature for scientific activities^a	Very good satisfaction with life			
never, rarely, sometimes	34 (42%) / 80	0.04	0.003–0.70	0.027
<i>Model statistics AIC 103,337; R² 0.308; HL: χ^2 2,916; df 7; p 0.893</i>	3 (75%) / 4	Ref.		
Thawing of the frozen ground causes problems, individually^a				
no	14 (31%) / 45	0.31	0.10–0.91	0.033
<i>Model statistics AIC 104,649; R² 0.291; HL: χ^2 3,941; df 8; p 0.862</i>	23 (59%) / 39	Ref.		

Table 4 (continued)

	Yes (n / %) / total	OR	95% CI	p-value
Challenges associated with the physical environment^a				
not important, little important, important very important	11 (30%) / 37	0.33	0.11–0.98	0.045
<i>Model statistics AIC 93,793; R² 0.314; HL: χ^2 8,501; df 7; p 0.291</i>	22 (56%) / 39	Ref.		
Life balance, very strong				
Challenges associated with housing, buildings, roads^a				
not important, a little important, important very important	5 (28%) / 18	0.14	0.04–0.53	0.004
<i>Model statistics AIC 95,175; R² 0.290; HL: χ^2 7,718; df 7; p 0.358</i>	41 (69%) / 59	Ref.		
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by local authorities^a				
no	16 (70%) / 23	3.38	1.00–11.41	0.050
<i>Model statistics AIC 107,792; R² 0.194; HL: χ^2 3,925; df 8; p 0.864</i>	33 (56%) / 59	Ref.		
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by national authorities^a				
no	27 (75%) / 36	6.74	2.05–22.14	0.002
<i>Model statistics AIC 100,011; R² 0.299; HL: χ^2 4,569; df 7; p 0.802</i>	22 (48%) / 46	Ref.		
Enough has been done to adapt or face impacts related to thawing by the global community^a				
no	27 (71%) / 38	4.88	1.57–15.23	0.006
<i>Model statistics AIC 102,164; R² 0.260; HL: χ^2 6,498; df 8; p 0.483</i>	21 (49%) / 43	Ref.		
Feelempowered to face changens				
Challenges associated with hunting and harvesting^b				
not important, a little important	19 (31%) / 61	5.60	1.14–27.44	0.034
<i>Model statistics AIC 58,029; R² 0.483; HL: χ^2 5,030; df 8; p 0.754</i>	11 (52%) / 21	Ref.		

Abbreviations: AIC: Akaike information criterion; R²: Nagelkerke R²; Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test (HL)

^a Adjusted for: age, gender, nationality (Scandinavian / others), employment situation

^b Adjusted for: age, gender, nationality (Scandinavian / others)

resources and financial situation, too. Tourism was seen as a problem in Svalbard. People felt that not enough has been done to adapt to climate change or stop it. However, it was felt that authorities do not act enough, and they do not realize the challenging and serious situation of climate change.

3.6. Summary of the results

Table 5 presents a summary of the results.

4. Discussion

The results provide an overall picture that people have good health, well-being, quality of life, and satisfaction with life in Longyearbyen, Svalbard – despite the impacts related to permafrost thaw and climate change. However, just over a third of the participants felt empowered to face changes related to permafrost thaw. Participants are aware and conscious of climate change and permafrost thaw. Many changes and challenges associated with permafrost thaw are being recognized in the living environment. This finding is supported by the current evidence that changes in environment, such as landscape and infrastructure damages due to permafrost thaw and climate change, are common and visible in Svalbard (Flyen et al., 2020; Jaskólski et al., 2018; Hovelsrud et al., 2020; Kaltenborn et al., 2020).

The main results can be summarized in two parts. *Firstly*, being in nature for recreational activities supported satisfaction with life and health. But, based on the logistic regression analysis, recognizing that permafrost thaw leads to challenges associated with hunting and harvesting seemed to decrease the feeling of empowerment to face changes related to permafrost thaw. *Secondly*, based on the logistic regression analysis, generally recognizing that permafrost thaw causes problems personally supported satisfaction with life and balanced life. Specifically acknowledging that challenges are very importantly associated with infrastructure (housing, buildings and roads) and the physical environment seemed to increase well-being, quality of life and satisfaction with life. The feeling that enough has not been done to adapt or face changes nationally or globally, also seemed to associate with quality life and life balance.

It can be that recognizing challenges associated with hunting and harvesting decreased the feeling of safety and security. People had noticed risks out in nature due to climate change. For hunting and harvesting it is necessary to go further into nature, and therefore it may be possible to realistically notice acute or long-term challenges in the environment that impact these actions in nature, compared to participants who assessed that challenges are not that important. It has been

found that in Svalbard, different natural hazards e.g., avalanches, rockfalls, unstable mountain slopes, or mudflows occur, which put infrastructure at risk, but also negatively impact peoples' feeling of safety (Jaskólski et al., 2018; Kaltenborn et al., 2020). Longyearbyen has faced serious fatal avalanches twice, in 2015 and again in 2017, both hitting houses (Jaskólski et al., 2018). As the results of our study showed, people had noticed avalanches and landslides, which negatively affected their feeling of safety. As has been shown by Lujala and colleagues (Lujala et al., 2015), a personal experience of natural-hazard related damage has the largest impact on peoples' perceptions of climate change and associated risks, while merely living in an exposed area does not significantly influence concerns about climate change. However, based on the authors' knowledge, there are no research evidence available to explain how these events impact mental well-being. There is evidence that acute events in climate are putting people at risk and in danger, with further effects on mental well-being (Bourque and Cunsolo Willox, 2014; Palinkas and Wong, 2020; Cianconi et al., 2020).

According to Roser-Renouf and colleagues (Roser-Renouf et al., 2016), being aware of the danger of climate change, but not having the knowledge and resources to handle the situation, is challenging. People are more likely to act on climate change when they feel they have knowledge about the situation, and they feel more empowered (Hartmann et al., 2018; Aitken et al., 2011). The mental impacts of climate change depend on the feeling of empowerment and ability to be resilient (Gifford and Gifford, 2016). The capacity to adapt is related to knowledge and awareness of the situation (Roser-Renouf et al., 2016; Hayes et al., 2019). These findings from the literature can also explain the results related to acknowledging problems of permafrost thaw and assessing challenges associated with the physical environment and infrastructure as very important. Participants who assessed these challenges as very important were more likely to rate their well-being, quality of life, and satisfaction with life as very good. In addition, based on the results of the open questions, people felt adaptation is feasible and essential. Research from mainland Norway has furthermore found that the need to adapt must be recognized for people to take action in the face of climate change (Dannevig and Hovelsrud, 2015). The results show that this need is indeed recognized in Svalbard and thus indicate the capacity to adapt. However, as Dannevig and colleagues conclude (Dannevig et al., 2013) on research from mainland Norway,

Table 5
Themes: Descriptive summary of challenging and supportive factors.

Themes / relationships (summary)	Well-being	Quality of life	Satisfaction with life	Life balance	Feeling of empowerment	Self-rated health
Being in nature for recreation activities	-	-		-	-	
Challenges associated with hunting and harvesting	-	-	-	-		-
Recognizing that permafrost thaw is causing problems	-	-				
Challenges are associated with infrastructure or physical environment				-		
Enough has not been done to adapt / face impacts nationally or globally	-		-		-	-
Risks that will affect the community e.g., changes in nature				-	-	-

- no statistically significant association found

successful adaptation is not only dependent on individuals' perceptions of changes, but rather hinges on engaged officials and is currently being impeded by a lack of clear adaptation policies and allocated resources. It has been found that adaptation requires assessment of the situation, development of strategies, and preparedness of the community but also political preparedness, on different levels (Roser-Renouf et al., 2016; Hayes et al., 2019). Additionally, it requires resources and social collaboration and communication (Hayes et al., 2019).

Considering research conducted in other areas in the Arctic, especially focusing on Indigenous people, the situation with climate change is not easy. According to Brubaker and colleagues (Brubaker et al., 2011), communities in Arctic Alaska have faced an increased risk of injuries and infectious diseases, and lower food and water security. Impacts and damages to the living environment have resulted in higher levels of mental stress and burden. Climate changes have serious consequences; for example, some communities may have to be relocated due to erosion or permafrost thaw (Bronen and Chapin, 2013; Hamilton et al., 2016). Similar consequences have been found by Filippova (2020) from Yakutia, Russia, where flooding has led to relocation of villages. It has caused further social challenges, e.g., separation of members of reindeer herding and hunting families. MacDonald and colleagues (MacDonald et al., 2015) have found that changed weather conditions, e.g., changes in ice, snow and temperatures, resulted in difficulties and risks to safety when accessing and being in nature. However, they found factors among Inuit youth that protected well-being when living surrounded by climate change, e.g., spending time in nature, having their own traditional culture, good personal relationships and being generally active in life (MacDonald et al., 2015). In a way, climate change has always been a part of youths' lives, and their knowledge is essential when investigating climate change (MacDonald et al., 2013). However, Kowalczewski and Klein (2018) found that, overall, climate change threatened the traditional culture and identity among Sámi youth. Among other difficulties, it challenged being a reindeer herder now or in the future (Kowalczewski and Klein, 2018; Stoor et al., 2015). Impacts may result in increasing safety risks due to weather changes in the nature, but also herders experienced anxiety due to fear of the future related to cultural continuity and economic development (Kowalczewski and Klein, 2018). Still, despite the challenges that climate change is causing, it can also create new options for people, as it has been found in studies related to Greenland (Timlin et al., 2021a; Nuttall, 2010; Tejssner, 2013). People should not be seen as outsiders of the situation – they should be seen as active, an example of how to live with changes (Stoor et al., 2015).

Based on the binary logistic regression analysis, participants who felt not enough has been done by national authorities and the global community to adapt or face changes related to permafrost thaw were more likely to have strong quality of life or balanced life. It can be that global discussion and future actions related to climate change are providing hope for people, and they feel the situation is not hopeless. According to Olsen and colleagues (Olsen et al., 2020), people in Longyearbyen are generally active, they have knowledge and are aware of changes related to the environment. This may support adaptation and a vision for the future. When providing information about climate change and its effects on well-being, it is essential to provide relevant information but with a positive approach, and with hope and solutions (Gifford and Gifford, 2016). For example, public campaigns and policies to reduce local climate threats are important (Roser-Renouf et al., 2016).

People are more highly educated in Svalbard compared to mainland Norway (Statistics Norway, 2016). Tourism, research, and education constitute the main economic pillars in Longyearbyen (Saville, 2018). It may be that local people have knowledge of climate change and therefore have tools to handle the current situation. Also, the high yearly turnover of residents can explain the result too. People are not impacted by permafrost challenges for a long time – it is more likely short term and permafrost thaw is a slow process. Additionally, only a minority of people living in Svalbard live in an owned house (10%) as the majority

of residents live in rental houses (Statistics Norway, 2016). It can be that acknowledged infrastructure challenges and impacts of permafrost thaw do not necessarily have such serious consequences among people living in rental apartments compared to the situation of owning the house and having further economic challenges due to damages and renovation costs. Perhaps people are not feeling as personally responsible for dealing with the impacts of climate change as in other areas. Also, it may be that people are not as vulnerable and marginalized as Indigenous peoples from across the Arctic.

This study has some limitations that need to be addressed. The study sample is small, which has limited the power of the statistical analysis and the variety of the investigated factors. Cronbach's alpha of sum variable (0.840) was good (Tavakol and Dennick, 2011) and overall, the goodness of fit of the modes was mediocre. It would have been interesting to investigate self-rated health by logistic regression analysis to get a more comprehensive view of this area. Health is often seen as physical health, and closer investigation of it requires more specific observations. Moreover, it must be acknowledged that questions of dependent variables were mainly placed at the end of the questionnaire, which can affect the answers of participants and assessments of their self-rated health (Q 37) and well-being, quality of life, and satisfaction with life (Q 38). Instead, feeling of empowerment was question 12. Participants' personal health and well-being situation at the time of the survey can be complex, as there may be many factors that affect the assessment of the investigated dependent variables either negatively or positively. The individual's current health and well-being situation, together with the situation of the environment, may affect the ability to adapt (Fresque-Baxter and Armitage, 2012).

More research should be conducted with a larger study sample. Due to the small sample size of this study, no generalization or strong conclusions can be made. With a larger study sample, it would be beneficial to further investigate the found associations more specifically by looking at the role of education, stable job and income, language and nationality etc., in relation to the awareness of the problems caused by permafrost thaw and the challenges related to them. Additionally, it would be important to compare the effects and opinions among younger and older participants, since there might be differences among different age groups. The data of our study was collected between August and January; however, the results may have differed if the data was collected during summertime due to experiences related to the certain time of the year. The results may not only have been affected by seasonal changes, but there can also be different views and experiences depending on the living place in Svalbard. As Onarheim and colleagues have found (Onarheim et al., 2014), warming has been higher in Northern Svalbard compared to areas further south. Also, there is little research available from Russian settlements on Svalbard, Barentsburg, and Pyramiden on climate change impacts and adaptation, which would allow a detailed comparison. Vlahov's (Sokolickova et al., 2022) research from Barentsburg indicates that the climate change and adaptation discourse is virtually absent in this Russian coal mining company town, and that environmental concerns are restricted to practical and visible issues such as waste management.

Qualitative interviews would be beneficial for further research when exploring impacts and adaptation processes on health and overall well-being more deeply. However, the results provide new information about the investigated area, more specifically regarding the holistic wellness, the strength to face permafrost thaw and the elements of the good life of people living with permafrost thaw. The dependent variables offer a comprehensive description of the life of participants. Multidisciplinary research provides a wide view of the current situation of people in Longyearbyen, Svalbard that reflects the life and living conditions of people.

5. Conclusions

Climate change and permafrost thaw are impacting peoples' lives in

Longyearbyen, Svalbard and environmental changes have been noticed. Despite recognized impacts and challenges, people appear to live good, comprehensive, and satisfied lives. Nature had an important, supportive role. People may have knowledge about the impacts of permafrost thaw, and they want to adapt to the changes – this may support and help dealing with impacts and facing them, especially regarding infrastructure. People may feel they have individually done enough to adapt to changes, but more actions are needed from national and global authorities. Wider actions are essential in order to support the people surrounded by climate change in Svalbard. However, this requires cooperation between communities, authorities locally and nationally, education and resources. In addition, more comprehensive research with a larger study sample, is needed to investigate the specific impacts on holistic well-being and living conditions due to the complexity of the relationship between people and research questions.

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The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crsust.2021.100122>.

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